

**RECYCLING
POST-CONSUMER
WOOD WASTE
INTO NEW
FIBREBOARDS
(MDF)**

**PROJECT INNOVATION
FACTSHEET**

Contributing to the EU's circular bioeconomy, reintegrating end-of-life panels into production helps optimise wood use, extend product lifecycles, stores carbon and reduce dependence on virgin wood.

ACHIEVEMENTS

Lab results

- Fibres from post-consumer fibreboards recovered via modified thermo-mechanical pulping process (mTMP, IHD) and Dieffenbacher's wet process incorporated into new fibreboards at 15% and 25%. The lower percentage yielded better fibreboard performance.
- Properties largely matched reference panels, while internal bond, panel density and surface quality required some optimisation.

Industrial results

- Well sorted and clean post-consumer solid wood fibres were extracted through conventional thermo-mechanical pulping. Panels containing up to 25% recycled fibres met requirements (EN 622-5) with properties comparable to reference boards.
- Melamine impregnated decorative paper surfacing with no visual defects or processing issue. Migration testing EN 71-3 and toy safety compliance and maintained performance with recycled wood content.

APPLICATIONS

Medium-density fibreboard (MDF) is a wood-based panel made with fibres bonded with resin under heat and pressure.

It has a smooth surface ideal for lacquering and CNC machining. Used in furniture fronts, decorative interior fittings, wall cladding and panelling.

R&D CHALLENGES

- Secure steady, sufficient volumes of quality wood waste through improved logistics and expanded collection networks.
- Upgrade and modernise existing lines by implementing optimised sorting and cleaning to ensure clean, consistent feedstock.

PARTNERS

CONTACTS

SONAE ARAUCO

Portugal | Spain | Germany | South Africa

ADELAIDE ALVES

Group R&D Director

aalves@sonaearauco.com

[sonaearauco.com](https://www.sonaearauco.com)

SLU SWEDISH UNIVERSITY OF AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

Department of Forest Biomaterials and Technology - Division of Wood Science and Technology | Uppsala, Sweden

Stergios Adamopoulos

Professor, Wood Science

stergios.adamopoulos@slu.se

[slu.se](https://www.slu.se)

[More information:](#)

[in EcoReFibre on LinkedIn](#)

[ecorefibre.eu](https://www.ecorefibre.eu)

This document reflects the authors' views only and neither the Agency nor the Commission are responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

Photo credits: Sonae Arauco, InnovaWood.
Layout: Fovéa création.